

TERMS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND THEIR TRANSLATION WAYS INTO UZBEK

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***Abstract:** The article focuses on the mistakes made in the translation of English terms into Uzbek and information on how to correct them.*

***Key words:** semantic relations, terms, translation method, word combinations.*

There is much more to be said about the complex sentence than about the compound. This is due to several clauses, which are, however, connected with one another. For one thing, the semantic relations who can be expressed by subordination are more numerous and more varied than with coordination: all such relations as time, place, concession, purpose, etc. are expressly stated in complex sentences only. Then again, the means of expressing subordination are much more numerous. There is here a great variety of conjunctions: when, after, before, while, till, until, though, although, albeit, that, as, because, since; a number of phrases performing the same function: as soon as, as long as, so long as, notwithstanding that, in order that, according as, etc [1, 127].

For example: 1) She did not do the part as she had at rehearsal, but she was better (Dreiser, 212).

In Uzbek: U bu rolini repititisiya paytidek o'ynamadi, ammo yaxshiroq o'ynadi.

1) She was not sure, after it was all over, just how the trouble had begun

In Uzbek: U o‘zi ham bilmas edi, janjal nimadan chiqqanligini.

Besides, a certain number of conjunctive words are used: the relative pronouns who, which, that, whoever, whatever, whichever and the relative adverbs where, how, whenever, however, why, etc.

Thus, as examples: 1) He was a large and corpulent individual, surfeited with good clothes and good eating, who judged woman as another would horseflesh. (Dreiser, 416).

In Uzbek: Bu kishi savlatli va tez-tez oziqlangandan semirgan edi, ayollarga huddi zotli otlarga qarab tushunadigan kishilarga o‘xshab qararedi.

2) She was determined now, however, that her husband was abroad, and that, under no circumstances, would she let this go by unsettled (Dreiser, 226).

In Uzbek: Ammo u hozir o'z erini hayvonligini tushunib vaqil mishini jazosiz qoldirib bo'lmasligini angladi.

We may note that the boundary line between conjunctions and relative adverbs is not quite clearly drawn. We shall also see this when we come to the adverbial clauses introduced by the word when and those introduced by the word where.

Historically speaking, conjunctions develop from adverbs and one word or another may prove to be in an intermediate stage when there are no sufficient objective criteria to define its status. The notions of declarative, interrogative, and imperative sentence, and also that of exclamatory sentence appear to be applicable to some types of complex sentences as well. For instance, if the main clause of a complex sentence is interrogative or imperative, this implies that the complex sentence as a whole is also interrogative or imperative respectively.

Examples:

1) Why did she look so disturbed when he had asked her how many times Hurstwood had called?

In Uzbek: Gerstvu necha marta telefon qilgani haqida so'raganda, nimadan u havotirda edi?

2) She did not do the part as she had at rehearsal, but she was better.

In English: U bu rolini repititsiya paytidek o'ynamadi, ammo yaxshiroq o'ynadi.

Above we defined a complex sentence as a sentence containing at least one subordinate clause. Any classification of complex sentences is therefore bound to be based on a classification of subordinate clauses. This will accordingly be our next task. The problem of classifying subordinate clauses is one of the vexed questions of syntactic theory. Several systems have been tried out at various times, and practically each of them has been shown to suffer from some drawback or other. Some of the classifications so far proposed have been inconsistent, that is to say, they were not based on any one firm principle of division equally applied to all clauses under consideration. We will first of all point out what principles of classification are possible and then see how they work when applied to Modern English.

Such kind of difficulties can be met in translating political speeches. One of the unique characteristics of political speeches is the frequent use of rhetorical devices such as repetition, as shown in the above sentence. Repetition is mostly used to emphasize a point. In the second example above, he mentioned the word *ish* ('work') several times to stress that his Cabinet focuses on *ishlash* ('working'); hence, the name of his cabinet is *Ishchi kabinet* (Working Cabinet). For this sentence, the translator also maintains the repetition in the translation. In translating sentences with a rhetorical device like this, adopting semantic translation method can be regarded as the right strategy. The repetition of certain

words or keywords is certainly not applied without reasons. In this example, the word *ish* is repeated three times and carries a meaning that the President wanted to put emphasis on the word *ish*. In fact, the word *ish* itself can be regarded as the general theme of the speech if we read the speech as a whole.

Therefore, semantic translation method can be applied when translating sentences with rhetorical devices found in many political speeches. Changing the sentence structure or omitting the repetition, for example, might still convey the original message, but the sentence's distinct feature, which indicates a special intention, might not be conveyed in the translation. Thus, this sentence is translated with semantic translation method, evidenced by the rhetorical device maintained in the TT. Sentences with repetition are also found in another part of the speech as follows.

References:

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